

A biographical take on interdisciplinarity: exploring disciplinary mobilities and power relationships of the professors of biological sciences

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Scientific elites are often defined as those who obtain significant scientific credibility based on various indicators, including citations, major scientific prizes, funded projects, and impact (Larivière et al. 2010). Conversely, academic elites are usually defined as individuals who hold concrete power within academic institutions, such as rectors of universities or members of committees involved in financing and promoting scientific activities (Bourdieu 1997). We propose to focus on professors as key actors in the production and transmission of knowledge, who can be endowed either with various volume of scientific and/or academic power. As such, their careers are crucial to understand the power dynamics underlying the symbolic hierarchy of knowledge and disciplines (Bourdieu 2001; Morgan et al. 2022).

Bourdieu's sociological research program provides insights into the structuring of scientific fields: relatively autonomous faculties, grounded in scientific capital, are associated with traditional scientific disciplines, while mondain academics possess temporal capital, granting them power over science-related matters (Bourdieu 1984). Scientific fields are hierarchized by social distinctions and characterized by unequal distribution of resources throughout scientific careers. These careers follow distinct phases and turning points; are embedded within institutional and structural contexts at different levels; and are subject to intense inequalities based on ascriptive characteristics (Abbott 2001; Hareven & Masaoka 1988). The degree of standardization of careers also informs on the relative autonomy of disciplines and the variations that exists in their organizational and cognitive frameworks (Bourdieu 1991; Benz & Rossier 2022).

The biological sciences offer an intriguing case for studying the relationship between power and epistemic structures. Mayr's seminal article (1961) outlined what he sees as the root the

division of biological sciences into two competitive groups, namely functional and evolutionary biologists. This division stems from differing epistemological approaches to the question of life and its causes. Functional biologists focus on proximal causes, emphasizing direct cause-effect relationships at the microbiological level, whereas evolutionary biologists prioritize historical explanations of ultimate causes at the macrobiological level. Recent developments in fields such as evodevo and epigenetics have prompted scholars to explore potential convergences between these approaches (Laland et al. 2011; Alizon & Method 2018). Still, scholarship in the sociology of science rather attest of a long-lasting division of labor between several "islands" (Larregue et al. 2020).

We ask two questions: (1) What are the epistemic divides that structure today's field of the biological sciences, and do they correspond to Mayr's distinction between functional and evolutionary biologists? (2) What are the explaining social factors behind these epistemic distinctions? To investigate the extent to which epistemic divisions in the biological sciences relate to social distinctions, we focus on an original database of all professors of biology in Switzerland between 2008 and 2020 (n=465). Information on entire careers from 20 to 50 years old is combined with information on all professors' projects funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and their scientific production, thanks to the Web of Science database.

Our analyses proceed in two steps. First, we aim to map the epistemic structure of the biological sciences, thanks to both network analysis and topic modelling on scientific abstracts (DiMaggio et al. 2013; Kropp & Larsen 2022). This first step allows us to identify the main principles of epistemic distinction among the professors of biological sciences, thus, to answer our first

research question. In a second step, we aim to understand the social factors behind these distinctions. By employing sequence analysis (Abbott & Hrycak 1990), we rely on information on professors' careers as pathways of accumulation of credit (Merton 1968; Bol et al. 2018), with their specific duration and structure, turning points or critical events that can have various effects depending on the time at which they occur. In addition, we aim to transform information on scientific production into sequences to identify epistemic trajectories (Henriksen & Seabrooke 2017; Benz and Rossier 2023). Such an approach will help us understand the relationship between the structure of institutional and epistemic careers, i.e. between international and disciplinary mobilities or interdisciplinarity and the access to prestigious positions, and the epistemic structure of the biological sciences.

We assume that a combination of relational and sequential approaches will help us understand how scientific habitus, i.e., the cognitive and incorporated structure of preferences and values, result from career and is influenced by both disciplinary mobilities and the succession of positions occupied. Furthermore, a focus on professors as scientific elites will allow us to explore the embeddedness of epistemic distinctions in power relationships.

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